

Compensatory Pulmonary Hyperinflation after Destruction of the Contralateral Lung by a Cystic Adenoid Malformation (Case Report)

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ABSTRACT

We report the case of a cystic adenoid malformation of the lung discovered in a 17-year-old patient with a history of repeated respiratory infections in childhood, with a history of passive smoking by his father, who presented with exertional dyspnoea associated with left chest pain with a productive cough bringing back greenish sputum resistant to symptomatic treatment. Imaging revealed a totally destroyed left lung with compensatory hyperinflation of the right lung. The patient underwent surgery. A left pneumonectomy was performed, with the discovery of significant compensatory hyperinflation of the right lung, visible by thoracotomy, and the postoperative course was straightforward. Anatomopathological study of the surgical specimen confirmed the diagnosis of a cystic adenoid malformation of the lung.

Keywords: Cystic adenoid malformation of the lung; Hyperinflation ; Surgical resection

INTRODUCTION

Cystic adenomatoid malformations of the lung (CAML) are the most common congenital lung malformation [1]. Their incidence is estimated at one in 25,000 to one in 35,000 pregnancies [2]. Diagnosis is anatomopathological. The "cysts" correspond to dilated airways, lined by respiratory epithelium resting on more or less richly vascularised musculo-elastic connective tissue. They communicate with adjacent lung tissue. CAML are often classified according to the criteria of Stocker et al [3]. However, this classification remains unsatisfactory, as it is purely descriptive and lacks any underlying pathophysiological justification. Type I CAML present one or more large cysts (> 2 cm) bordered by a high, pseudo-stratified epithelium.

Type II CAML consist of multiple smaller cysts (< 1 cm), bordered by high ciliated or cuboidal epithelium, rarely pseudo-stratified. The macroscopic appearance of type III lesions is solid, non-cystic; micro-cysts are seen microscopically, and the majority of the lesion consists of immature structures suggestive of the pseudo-glandular stage of lung development. The rest of the upstream and downstream lung is normal [3].

The CAML are most often unilateral and unifocal, confined to one lung lobe [4]. They have been described in both the right and left lobes, and seem to predominate in the lower lobes [1]. A multifocal or bilateral cystic lesion,

although possibly CAML, raises the possibility of other diagnoses, in particular pulmonary pleuroblastoma (PPB) [5].

The CAML share common features with other congenital pulmonary malformations (pulmonary sequestration, bronchial atresia, congenital lobar emphysema). Like sequestrations, they have systemic vascularisation in 10 to 50% of cases [1]. A microcystic parenchyma typical of type II CAML is observed in some bronchial atresias [6]. These overlapping phenotypes strongly suggest that these malformations, which have different names, share common pathophysiological mechanisms. Recent recommendations have been to give preference to a description of visible anomalies rather than the traditional nomenclature [7].

OBSERVATION:

A 17-year-old patient with a history of recurrent respiratory infection in childhood, and a history of passive smoking by his father, presented for 4 months with exertional dyspnoea associated with left chest pain and a productive cough producing greenish sputum resistant to symptomatic treatment.

Sputum was negative for acid-fast bacilli, white blood count $8000/\text{mm}^3$, CRP 30, and hydatid serology negative. The multiple cystic lesion in the left posterobasal tomography corresponded to a left lung that was totally destroyed with significant compensatory hypertrophy of the right lung with a retro sternal hernia towards the left haemothorax, which it occupied almost entirely (Figures 1 and 2).

The indication for surgery was given and the patient underwent a conservative left posterolateral thoracotomy without any muscle section, which revealed a totally destroyed left lung with significant compensatory hyperinflation of the right lung visible through his thoracotomy (Figure 3). The patient underwent a left pneumonectomy (Figures 5 and 6). The post-operative course was straight forward and the patient was discharged at 8 days post-operatively.

Pathological examination of the surgical specimen was consistent with a cystic adenoid malformation of the lung. The patient was reviewed at 2 weeks, 1 month, 3 months and 6 months with good clinical progression and radiological stability (Figure 6).

Figure 1 and 2: Multiple cystic lesions in the posterior basal left lung correspond to a left lung which is totally destroyed with significant compensatory hyperinflation of the right lung.

Figure 3: Hyperinflation of the right lung visible by left posterolateral thoracotomy.

Figure 4 and 5: left pneumonectomy specimen (lung destroyed)

Figure 6: X-ray of the patient after one month of surgery

DISCUSSION

Congenital cystic adenomatoid malformation is a rare disease, first described in 1897 by Staerk [8]. Its incidence is one case per 25,000 to 35,000 pregnancies [9]. Most cases have been described in neonates or children, very rarely in adults, with 90% of patients reported to be under two years old [10].

This malformation results from a localised arrest in the development of the foetal bronchial tree, around the sixth week of pregnancy. Lung development comprises several successive stages: the embryonic stage (fourth to eighth week) during which the main bronchi are formed, the pseudoglandular stage (fifth to 16th week) during which the bronchial tree is formed and the acini are born. Between the tenth and 14th weeks, the five lobar bronchi are present, as are 70% of the bronchial divisions. This is followed by the ductal, saccular and alveolar stages [11]. During each of these stages, an organogenesis anomaly may occur, leading to a malformation of the respiratory tract. Congenital cystic adenomatoid malformation occurs during the first two stages.

Advances in antenatal ultrasound have made it possible to detect congenital lung malformations as early as the first trimester of pregnancy; however, CAML are most often diagnosed during the fifth-month ultrasound [12].

The majority of patients are asymptomatic during the neonatal period [13]. Follow-up of asymptomatic patients at birth includes a standard chest X-ray, taken before discharge from the maternity hospital. This may appear normal even if there is a persistent lesion. Its sensitivity has been evaluated at 61% compared with CT [14]. CT with injection has a sensitivity close to 100%. It is generally performed in the first two to three months of life in asymptomatic patients. The CAML appear as cystic lesions of variable size, or as hyperinflated areas [15]. They sometimes have a solid appearance, particularly in the first few days of life, due to retention of pulmonary fluid [15]. CT scans look for associated systemic vascularisation and may point towards a differential diagnosis (lobar emphysema, sequestration, bronchial atresia). It determines the size of the lesion and assesses its impact on the adjacent lung parenchyma and mediastinal structures.

Twenty per cent of patients are symptomatic at birth [13]. Neonatal respiratory distress is the most frequent complication [16]. It can be severe, requiring intensive care with assisted ventilation. In the absence of symptoms during the perinatal period and in the absence of surgical treatment, approximately 3% of patients develop symptoms at a median age of seven months [13]. Pulmonary infections are the most common complication beyond the neonatal period [15]. Other complications described include pneumothorax and haemothorax [15]. Pneumothorax is rare, however, and should be investigated in patients with pleuropneumoblastoma (PPB) [5]. In the absence of surgical excision, pulmonary lesions rarely disappear. Aziz et al. followed 17 asymptomatic patients from birth with regular CT scans for an average of three years [17]. No disappearance was observed. In another series, Sauvat et al. observed CT disappearance during the first year of life in two patients out of 29 who were asymptomatic at birth [18]. In these two series, the diagnosis of CAML was strongly presumed by imaging, but not confirmed histologically. The most controversial complication of MAKP is its potential malignant transformation [15]. CAML are likely to degenerate into PPB in childhood, or into bronchioloalveolar carcinoma (BAC) later in life. There appears to be a clear link between CAML type I and BAC [19]. Atypical mucinous cell foci, found only in CAML type I, are thought to be at the origin of the malignant degeneration of CAML into BAC [20]. They share the same chromosomal abnormalities as those seen in CBA, but these chromosomal abnormalities are absent in the cystic epithelium and adjacent normal tissue [20]. However, the number of described cases of CBA in young patients with CAML remains very low. The relationship between CAML and

SCH is less clear-cut. Some believe that CAML may degenerate into PPB [21], while others believe that the two lesions are of different origins [5].

Surgical resection should be performed when the diagnosis is suspected. Cases of malignant transformation, particularly into bronchioalveolar carcinoma, have been reported in the literature [22].

The approach is usually a posterolateral thoracotomy, allowing a precise assessment of the lesion and a systematic resection. Videothoracoscopy has been used by some authors, with no superiority over conventional thoracotomy [23].

Surgical resection should be as systematic as possible to avoid recurrence and possible degeneration [24]. Pneumonectomies have been performed for multilobar localisations.

In our case, the patient presented with a totally destroyed left lung with very significant compensatory hyperinflation of the left lung visible by left thoracotomy. The indication for left pneumonectomy was therefore retained by our team.

CONCLUSION

Cystic adenoid malformations of the lung should be suspected in the presence of cystic images in adults. They present a risk of malignant degeneration and require surgical resection in all cases.

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest in relation to this article.

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